

Revolutionary Strategies in Wale Okediran's *The Boys at the Border*

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Abstract

*Challenges of insecurity, especially in Africa, have become very problematic. In political, religious, economic, and marital terms, almost all parts of Africa are embroidered in one form of upheaval or the other. This paper investigates and analyses the nature of insecurity buttressed in Wale Okediran's *The Boys at the Border* and demonstrates that oppression, brutality and lack of respect for human lives are its hallmarks in Africa. The paper shows the various means by which novelists hope the challenge of insecurity can be addressed. It finds that desperate and revolutionary solutions must be adopted if the challenge of insecurity is to be addressed effectively. The research was anchored using Marxism Theory. The novelist offers suggestions on how the challenge of insecurity can be tackled. It concludes that, as portrayed in the novel, open confrontation with bad resistance and selfless sacrifice are the major revolutionary strategies required to fight the menace of insecurity.*

Keywords: Leadership, Politics, Corruption, Insecurity, Oppression

Introduction

The issue of security has become a major factor in academic seminars and conferences just as the efforts to counter it has become an important feature in state policies. Actually, security issues determine the way individual countries organize themselves and relate to other countries. In fact, security considerations dictate the way nations safeguard themselves and relate to one another. The rise of terrorism in the 21st century has worsened the security situation globally, for there is hardly any part of the globe today that is immune to the attacks of terrorists. There are many problems facing Nigeria and most of them have contributed to the insecurity over the land. The problems include terrorism, militancy, agitation for cessation, armed robbery, kidnapping, illiteracy, corruption, poverty and youth restiveness. This work looks at the aspect of corruption as portrayed in Wale Okediran's *The Boys at the Border*.

Wale Okediran, is a medical doctor, award-winning writer, art administrator, and politician. Okediran was the National President of the Association of Nigerian Authors (ANA) from 2006 to 2009 and is currently the Secretary-General of the Pan African Writers Association. He served as a Member of the Nigerian Federal House of Representatives from 2003 to 2007 and has consulted for several global and local development organizations. He is the founder of the first writers' residency in Nigeria, the Ebedi Institutional Writers Residency in Iseyin, Oyo State, an initiative that is building and motivating writers across Africa. And the convener of the Read Across Nigeria (RAN) project. Okediran has authored fourteen novels, one of which is the highly acclaimed novel *Tenants of the House*, a fictional account of his time as a member of the House of Representatives. The young Okediran was greatly interested in both the humanities and sciences from a young age. He was fascinated by films and galleries as much as he was fascinated by physics experiments and the wonders of chemistry. This love of two contrasting disciplines made it difficult for him to decide where to major. Then he found out he did not have to throw away one for the other and decided to do both. He was a member of the press club and a science student in secondary school. It was during this time that he first fell in love with writing. He said, "My first experience with writing was at school. I joined the press club, and that was where I had my first interaction with writing." Dr. Okediran's journey and career in writing are very interesting, as he did not set out to write prose at the beginning of his writing journey. "I started writing poems first, but as time passed, I desired to try something different. I started writing prose because poetry was a limitation

to me, and I did not like to be limited by anything at all. The prose was an escape from the limitations poetry made me feel." Dr Okediran has published many works, from his detailed medical essays to his books. He has written many books and explored a lot of important topics. He is inspired by everyday life and the sheer beauty of human behaviour and existence. He finds meaning in things that others may overlook or consider mundane. 'When I find a thing worthy of writing about, I try to write about it in the most glaring ways.' The truth and relatability of his writing are two things that stand out about them as found in the novel under study, *The Boys at the Border*.

The study deploys Marxist theory in the analysis, because Marxism challenges all forms of societal and individual exploitations which are well illustrated in the novel under consideration. Habib M. A. B. the founder of Marxism, "(Karl Heinrich or Marx 1818-1883) was a German political, economic and philosophical theorist and revolutionist." (532) As a revolutionary, Marx writes about the pitiable conditions of the oppressed. The destiny of the less privileged is controlled by capitalist and politicians who perpetrate insecurity through selfish socio-economic and political policies, institutions and laws. Marx raises the consciousness of the exploited workers by exposing employers' antics. In an unpublished number of the magnates of capital, grows the mass of misery, oppression, slavery, degradation and exploitation. But with this too grows the revolt of the working class, a class always increasing in number and disciplined, united, organized by the very mechanism of the process of production itself." (532)

Marxist ideology sets the stage for struggles between oppressed and the oppressor. Karl Marx tries to see the oppressed 'working class' liberated from disadvantaged system of politics and economy. Charles E. Bressler says that Marx and Engels "Maintain that the capitalists or the bourgeoisie have successfully enslaved the working class or the proletariat through economic politics and production of good." (164) Bressler and Habib capture Marx's main argument that any form of economic or political system that creates opportunities for one class of people to oppress and exploit another class, must be pulled down. This notion is well captured in the assertion of Bressler that,

"As a direct result of division of labour within the capitalist society, workers no longer have contact with the entire process of producing, distributing and consuming material goods. Individuals are cut off from the full value of their work as well as from each others, each performing discrete functional roles assigned to them by the bourgeoisie. To rid society of this situation, Marx believes that the government must own all industries and control the

economic production of a country to protect the people from the oppression of the bourgeoisie." (164)

As noted by Bressler, workers are cheated by their employers who hardly give them what they deserve. Marxism is, therefore, a remedy to the exploitation which workers suffer. The bourgeoisie and those who represent their interest hate Marxism because it makes the proletariat revolutionary. It, therefore, creates conflict in the society. The need for a radical change is largely behind the ideology of Marxism because it engages a society in a serious conflict that aims to liberate those under capitalists' shackles. Marxism does not celebrate oppression and exploitation. Rather, it encourages revolution. Solomon Maynard supports this view when he says that

"Marxism is the symbolism of dialectical conflict of drama, of the unity of opposites of revolutionary change, of matter and man in motion, constantly transcending the moment, pointing into the future."(17) As every society moves from one stage to another, conditions of life change. Such changes would include the overthrow of the dominant capitalist ideology and the loss of power by those with money and privilege."(2089). As Carlos points out, Marxism seeks social justice for the oppressed. It does not support any form of exploitation that leaves a group of people cheated or disadvantaged. Carlos further lays bare the focus of Marxism when he says that, "Marxist criticism is concerned both with understanding the role of Politics, money, and power in literary works, and with redefining and reforming the way society distributes its resources among the classes."(2089) The employment of Marxism in the evaluation of African literature cannot be over emphasized. Failure of leadership, brutality, oppression and exploitation of the masses by the privileged often lead to serious insecurity and these have come under the attack by writers and critics. Marxism is the preferred ideology employed in most literary criticism because as ChidiAmuta says, "Marxism arose when and where it did as a result of determinate conditions primary among which was the target of capitalism, the alienation of labour, and the galvanization of working class consciousness. What is crucial in Marxism, therefore, is not the nationality of Marx and Engels but the practical contents of their ideas. And is the extent that more of the problems of contemporary Africa which also form the essential preoccupation of African literature, can be traced to capitalist

imperialism, the instrumentality of Marxist for dealing with that literature falls into place."(158-60)

Amuta is also of the view that capitalism is an enemy of the working class. Africans live a communal life and this contrasts capitalism that favours individuals. Capitalism empowers few individuals to lord it over majority of helpless workers. Capitalism, therefore, ensures insecurity. From all these observations, it is clear that the struggle to be free from oppression, brutality and death (which are aspects of insecurity), will continue between the oppressor and the oppressed. In addition, the oppressed will always look for novel means of breaking the bonds of oppression and casting away the yoke of servitude.

Okediran's *The Boys at the Border* dwells on the sufferings of the oppressed under a political system that is run by tyrants and other inhuman leaders. Ifejirika argues that in *The Boys at the Border*, Okediran presents the conflict between security officials at the nation's border and the business muggles who smuggle goods legally and illegally into the country in agreement to avert payment of official duty tax but rather settle the officials at the background. This is a clear case of greed and injustice. The security officials represent African leaders who exploit the masses in order to increase their own fortunes.

Okediran is a satirist who tries to use his work to reform the society. To do so, he writes to open the eyes of the masses and he encourages them to fight for their rights. Ujowundu also shares this worthy attribute of Okediran. Through the novel, Okediran educates and conscientises the oppressed. He encourages revolution against failed leaders and the political system. It hurts to know that the political systems of African states are weak and so, they make room for irresponsible leadership and followership. Reading *The Boys at the Border's* satirical message, Nwosu in his *Invisible Chapters*, notes that the failure of government has created loopholes that enables the rich to exploit the poor, "true, but you no see say na we ordinary people all these muggers-in-power dey use play the jackpot? Even oyibo people no wicked us like this. Government no be people? They know themselves."(52/72). What this means is that African governments have failed the masses. Through their inefficient policies, few individuals are made rich. This has widened the socio-economic gap between the rich and the poor. This engenders economic insecurity. According to Asika, Okediran also exposes African states' failure of governance and leadership collapse that precipitate insecurity.

Oppression in *The Boys at the Border*.

Perhaps, the first phase of insecurity in Africa is oppression of the people by those who should protect them. Kehinde, Osakede et al, observe that "the Nigerian society has never been well governed because of impunity and corruption, since it gained its political independence in 1960."(76-77). Those who govern most sectors in Nigeria use oppression to cow the people. Oppression engenders insecurity and elicits violent agitations. Adewonmi Samuel Idowu and Akinkurolere Susan Olajoke rightly note that "it is widely believed that politics should be practised in a way that dividends of democracy could be brought nearer to the people particularly those at the grassroots, but the reverse is the case in Nigeria context where politics is played by politicians to enrich their individual purses."(10-15). In *The Boys at the Border*, Okediran exposes the activities of the smugglers in collaboration with the security officers entrusted with the functions at the border whose duties include border services and to monitor the in cum out flow of human et vehicular movement. He hinged his anger and finding specifically on the custom officers. The reader is opened to this at the very beginning of the novel as the novelist captures, "They got Samuel! He was shot about half an hour ago: I am not sure, though my guess is that it could have been Lati Baba." My guess is that he did not declare all his trucks. He must have been trying to sneak off another convoy when Samuel intercepted it." We were just outside Iganna when Lati's convoy arrived as scheduled around ten in the evening. You remember he gave you twenty thousand naira at two thousand naira per truck."(1-2) One wonders the type of security these officials keep at the border where they engage in such sharp practices with smugglers that can chip in or out anything, authorized and unauthorized. From the above discussion, it is obvious there is mutual agreement between the custom and the smugglers. They serve their personal interest above that of the national security. This cuts across the custom officers both the high and might. Emeka Emodi's intention is actually not to serve the people. His real intention in connivance with Lati Baba, is to seize power, set up road blocks and detention centres, impose a levy on all the smugglers with little or no reserve for the nation as the reader was informed, "Cocoa and groundnuts are top on the list, unfortunately, the activities of smugglers have not allowed the country to be able to export these commodities as much as we would have liked to. For example, from cocoa alone, the country loses about six thousand tonnes every year. This at the present rate of five thousand naira per tonne comes to about three million naira. Same goes for groundnuts and other items like textiles, shoes and even refined oil which are being smuggled across the border."(6). This

act of oppression coming from a man who claims he serves the people is ironical. The activities of these smugglers throw the nation into problems. The smugglers route through the much dread Nigerian western border, leads to Benin Republic, which serves as the recipient of the cocoa smuggled out of Nigeria. This arrangement turns Benin, a country that does not grow much cocoa into a major exporter of the crop. Cocoa is smuggled out through more than hundred routes, out of which only fifty or so are known to the men of the customs and excise unit. This in turn destroys the economy of the nation.

The custom officers use fraudulent ways to lure the smugglers into the scheme. It becomes necessary to check customs' reckless ambition as they strike deals with smugglers thus, "We have no problem with you and we had already agreed on what to give you. I personally handed over the money to you last night."(10). The insensitive nature of our customs can not be overemphasized as they jump into unduly activities during official duties. They care more about stomach infrastructure as the novelist informs the reader through Bayo and Peter's visit to Lati on a murder investigation. They both yield for cold drinks, "That is fine. I would like a bottle of beer. And me too. Peter added as he removed his cap and threw it with a flourish on the empty seat beside him."(27). As soon as the beer tops started popping off and glasses were filled with the cold sparkling drinks, the officers stoop low to whatever assignment they come for. Lati, the gang leader becomes overwhelmed at the secret behind the officials' relaxation over beers instead of the assignment they come for and immediately went to meet Atere his boy behind the door and informed him to stop pouring incantations that the spell has got the officers. The dramatic irony here can not be overlooked. The smugglers captured and held the security officials to a halt instead of the other way round. This dwindles the growth of the nations agriculture, commerce and industry.

This amounts to national show of shame where the custom officer decides to wake to the call of his people's juju as a weapon to defend himself. This was possible as Bayo chose not to run away from the job rather he would revert to his people for an assistance through their charm,

"Transfer? You mean we should run away? Not me Bayo. What I will do is to take a few days of next weekend. I will go and see my people in the village for assistance. We too have very powerful JuJu in my place. I will go and prepare myself for the fight ahead and I promise you, when I come back, I will be adequately armed to cope with the problems at hand."(45).

Citizens promote crimes in the society. Some attach their inability to be sincere to duty on government's poor attitude to the welfare of the citizens. The situation is very similar in Nigeria where people get less from their leaders. There is large scale mismanagement in leadership. Osakede et al observe that "The leadership from 1960 has criminally managed the country's affairs, accumulated wealth at the expense of the national development and thrown the people over the precipice, where they now wallow in absolute poverty, illiteracy, hunger, rising unemployment, avoidable health crisis and insecurity."(76-87). This observation by Osakede et al is apt because they identify the causes of poverty, poor leadership and their effects. For the masses to succeed, they must stand their ground and refuse to be crushed by smugglers, the agent of oppression.

Lack of Respect for Human Lives

The ultimate indication of insecurity in Africa is the apparent lack of respect for human lives as shown in the novel. As a means of safeguarding his business, Lati Baba spares nothing not even human lives as the novelist depicts, "On top of all these negligence, the smugglers continue killing our boys."(36) The situational irony here is that the custom officials collect bribe and encourage the smugglers. They get at each other sometimes,

"Unfortunately, the third truck had a flat tyre and as we were changing it, the young customs man intercepted us. Despite my offer of two thousand naira for the three trucks, he insisted on taking six thousand naira. I told him I was broke but he persisted. Then he ordered me at gunpoint into his jeep. I became afraid and I... I"(20).

He chose to die for his personal interest as against that of his nation. Were they supposed to collect any money from those who use the road? Are they, the custom officers on the road for tax collection into their personal pocket as seen from the above discussion? With such arrangements and settlement with the smugglers who also see themselves as lords, they are ready to kill anyone on their way physically, socially, spiritually and otherwise. This is buttressed in the discussion with a custom officer as he shows concern over their safety. Peter told Bayo, " I am getting really worried about our safety in this place. It is obvious now that these smugglers are out to get us through any means. Apart from running away from their guns, we still have to avoid their charms and amulets."(44). This is a very clear picture of the disregard for human lives which is characteristic of all dictators. Human lives to them, are expendable and dispensable. They show no sympathy for the oppressed and do not hesitate to kill

people just to achieve their objective as Lati Baba ordered officer, "That bastard, Peter Ikoku, got me into this. I want him sacked immediately or at least removed from that our area. I am saying this for his own good because I know that some of the boys will be looking for a way of getting rid of him,"(60). From the above assertion, one wonders if there is any form of respect and honour to human dignity. Activities of known and unknown gunmen across the nation, claimed more unimaginable lives. The questions seeking for answer follow thus: How did we arrive here? Who should be held responsible for the lost? What is the way forward to solving this menace? Loss of human lives should be of great concern to both individuals, cooperate organizations and the government. Government must as a matter of urgency, put reliable policies on ground that would shape the individual's ideology towards positive thinking. The basic unit of the society, family, has a lot to offer to curb this societal ills. It is only rightful thinking that would sanitize our nation and make it free of individuals with negative minds. Lack of respect for human lives is further demonstrated in the novel when the week old baby was ill. The old women around used fire to design him, left him half dead before taking him to hospital. The nurse did not hide her feelings towards them, "You people are heartless. Why did you burn the baby so badly?"(46). Imagine the idea of reviving a convulsing baby with a burning log of wood from the fire. The smell of burning flesh float through the air, the baby cries out, "You see now, he is still alive, as soon as the baby stopped crying, the women again touched his left thigh with the burning log. The child was covered with burn wounds on his two thighs, abdomen and chest. Despite this, he continued convulsing. Let us put some pepper in his eyes, another woman suggested."(46). One from the above statements wonders the type of aid this child receives from mothers around. The novelist here condemns the attitude of local care givers who administer wrong treatment to sick and dying which cause more casualty in the society.

Revolutionary Strategies

A tense atmosphere characterised by insecurity, oppression, brutalisation, injustice and exploitation has occasioned victims of oppression to resort to open confrontation of bad leaders. According to Martin Luther king, "A second way that oppressed people sometimes deal with oppression is to resort to physical violence and corroding hatred."(23) It is only drastic measure from all involved that would bring a revolutionary mood across the nation. There should be some changes in a positive direction before we can experience this change. For this change to be achieved, people of all categories must be

ready to adjust and say no to vices, greed and selfishness that deface our society. Saying it would not change anything rather actions in the right direction would sanitize our world. Insecurity is a serious threat to human development. Okediran portrays this through one of the smugglers as he makes a u-turn. He condemns smuggling in his words thus, "Smuggling is a very dangerous business and since I am getting older every day, I should start looking for something less hectic to do."(139) In all fairness, our world can be made better through a collective effort of both individuals, government and cooperate organizations. The novelist shows this through one of his characters in his confession, "It is true that I ... I committed the offence but I will like the President to note that I am just being used as a scapegoat for an offence that is being widely practised amongst the top echelons of the society in this country. I think the government is also to blame for his having for a long time, turned a blind eye to such atrocities."(93)

This is a diplomatic confrontation that can tackle government's negligence. Custom officers have been a thorn in the flesh of many people due to their various acts of misconduct which portrayed Nigeria as a failed nation. Mrs Gladys Emodi notes that custom has failed the masses, "I think there is something we can start on. Next Thursday at 10 in the morning, Lati Baba will be at Alhaji Jibo's office to collect some bribe. If we could capture the scene either by camera or tape recorder, we could then use it."(72) Out of frustration, people become non-conformists. They go against the law. Acts of violence have increased due to government's failure. People use violence to agitate for social justice. Ordinarily, this is not ideal but it seems to be only language irresponsible governments understand. Okediran advocates moral as a viable option to confront the menace. He does not believe any one individual can be a Messiah, however, the people in a given society can save themselves.

Government must live up to expectations and shift away from various exposures workers face especially as regards their remuneration and welfare as this will curb corruption and insecurity as the novelist states, "I better let you know that I also got something from Lati Baba before Jibo did. One's salary is not enough to live on with the inflation"(99) Marxism supports movement or bodies that gather people under one umbrella with common ideology and goal. The quest for excessive material possessions blinds the overlords of every society. Powerful people seek to personalise the world, therefore, they want to control everything even the air the masses breath. This level of great and selfish ambition prevent equity and the inhabitants of society. It is these unjust individuals that Marxism fights against. If left unchecked, the ambition of the super rich will suffocate the poor.

That greed in the rich to acquire more at the expense of the poor creates insecurity and conflicts. Those below fight not just the selfish ambition of the rich but also the social, political, and economic structures that promote smart practices that further enrich the bourgeoisie. Marxism glorifies communalism, therefore, it calls for a revolt against those with selfish nature. This is expressed in the novel thus, "The problem of leadership, your excellency comes in at this juncture. When you have a director whose field officers are corrupt and instead of dealing with these officers, the director now turns round to accuse imaginary people like the army, police and even the fire brigade . . ."(35) Insecurity situation in most African society is so horrible that open confrontation and resistance become necessary revolutionary strategies. Corrupt and selfish people must not be celebrated. Those who seek personal gains in public office must be seen as enemies of progress as their activities promote insecurity. Okediran advocates open confrontation and tenacious resistance as revolutionary strategies to combat insecurity.

Conclusion

There are many problems facing Nigeria and most of them have contributed to the climate of insecurity that has beset the country. The novelist used fairly recent and very literary work to illustrate the points raised in this study and to underscore the fact that most of the newer writers who belong to a younger generation have, as their predecessors, contributed immensely to exposing the ills in our society with a view to providing new dimension as well as strategies in the task of regeneration and reorientation needed for a peaceful co-existence in the country. In the process of exploring the sources of insecurity in the society, they device fresh and new forms of narration that imbue their work with strong aesthetic appeal and technical success. In other words, these works not only treat serious themes, but also maintain artistic integrity and formal beauty. Okediran in his work, *The Boys at the Border*, calls for a revolution with a view to checking the excesses of those destroying the national values of every society.

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